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Research Article

A Survey of the Services of Public Libraries in Meeting the Information Needs of Post-Secondary School Students in Some Three Selected Public Libraries in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The role of Public Libraries in meeting the information needs of the Community cannot be neglected. The Library is meant to serve the needs of all and sundry in the society without any bias. The main objective of this study was to examine the services of the Public Libraries in meeting the information needs of Post Secondary School Students in Public Libraries in Nigeria. The study adopted a Descriptive Survey Design and the Simple Random Sampling Techniques was used to select one hundred and fifty respondents (Post-Secondary School Students) in three selected Public Libraries, that is, Oyo, Ogun and Kwara State Library Boards. The questionnaire was the instrument used to collect data for the study, while descriptive statistics with tables of frequencies and percentages was used in analysing the data.

The study revealed that the information needs of the Post-Secondary School Students were information on academic work, personal development and sports news and recreation. Different services rendered by Public Libraries were looked into. Inadequate information resources were the major factor militating against the Public Library services to the Post-Secondary School Students. Various reasons why post-secondary school students use the public library were also highlighted. It is recommended that adequate information resources be provided in Public Libraries so that information needs of the user can be met.

Keywords: Public Libraries, Information, Information needs, Post secondary school students, Library services.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a means of transmitting one's culture from one generation to another. It is the process of bringing about a relatively permanent change in human behaviour. As the oldest industry, it is the main instrument used by society to preserve, maintain and upgrade its social equilibrium. A society's future depends largely on the quality of its citizen's education. In all human societies, education is meant to pass on to the new generations the existing knowledge of their physical environment, to introduce individuals to the organization of society, to give them skills for performing their daily jobs, enjoying their daily jobs and enjoying their leisure, as well as inculcate sound morals in them for their own benefit and that of the society. In other words, education is a process by which the society assists the younger generation to understand the heritage of their past, participate productively in the society of the present as well as contribute to the future. Based on these reasons, it is therefore clear that education draws inspiration and nourishment from a society, but in turn, it contributes to the growth, renewal and development of that society.

The role of library in education cannot be underestimated. Newke (1995) defined libraries as repositories of knowledge or storehouses of written records of civilizations in various forms of the information package ... libraries play informational, recreational, research, cultural, educational roles. Amadi (1981) emphasized that "libraries in Europe and America exist to meet the cultural and information needs of their communities." According to Nwalo (2000), libraries are in the vanguard of information generation, acquisition, processing, organization and dissemination in institutions, groups and in society for self -development, organizational development as well as for national development. UNESCO in 1952 held a seminar on public library development in Ibadan Oyo State, Nigeria, with the following aims and objectives for public libraries:

- To support and reinforce programme of adult and fundamental education.
- To provide effective service for children and young people including requisite service for schools.
- To promote and stimulate reading for pleasure and recreation.
- To provide wherever needed adequate services for special groups in order to ensure availability of resources on equal terms to all members of the community.

In the broadest sense, libraries have existed almost as long as written records themselves. The instinct to preserve and passion to collect information have been the determining factor in their establishment, maintenance and development. A library is concerned with the collection, processing, storage and dissemination of recorded information for the purpose of reading, studying and consultation. In order for a library to attain this goal, many activities are performed by a library which translates into library and information services. Over the years, the external environment has been having a tremendous impact on the practice of the profession. As pointed by Aina (2004), library and information profession borrows from a number of disciplines, such as sociology, psychology, computer science, business, management, mathematics, statistics, marketing etc. thus, anything that impacts on any of these disciplines would have a direct influence on library and information science profession.

The public library system is a relative newcomer to the African information provision scene. It was not introduced until the middle of the twentieth century, at the end of the colonial era. The initial enthusiastic reception of these institutions by both the governments and the general public can be ascribed to the perception persisting at that time that they would serve as a remedy to serve existing educational problems as well as a tool in the process of national development (Abdullahi, 1998). A threefold role was designated to these institutions: to provide information to development agents and agencies, to support formal and informal rural education programs through the provision of materials to both students and teachers, and to serve as center for community education and cultural activities.

The post secondary school students form a large percentage of population of a modern society. They are made up of the students in the technical schools, colleges of agriculture and education, monotronics, polytechnics, schools of nursing, hygiene and universities; as such they need unrestricted access to recent and up-to-date information which can only be guaranteed in the library.

The services should be such that will motivate students to patronize libraries, encourage reading interest among young people, adolescent and provide opportunities for adults in seeking information needs, choosing books and magazines in sciences, sports, relaxations and personal problems. In order to fully render the services effectively, UNESCO Public library Manifesto (1972) stresses the need for public libraries to provide children with recorded experience of other people that will help them to grow in their information needs.

Access to information resources and services within the larger society cannot be achieved without involving public libraries because they "are one of the building blocks of the local information and knowledge infrastructure" (Tise, 2000). Furthermore, libraries embody a principle of rights of access to information and acquisition of knowledge by all categories of individuals in a society. In a nutshell, access to information without libraries is inconceivable because librarianship is concerned with literacy, intellectual freedom, and equity of information access for reconstruction, development and enhancing the quality of life. Abdulkarim (2010) noted that public libraries are expected to play an indispensable role in the life of the community they serve, one of which is the promotion of reading culture among members of the society, be it in the rural or urban settings. They are also expected to provide good information and reference centre for the masses through the building of collections that relates to local interest. This collection could be book and non book materials and should be properly organized, integrated and equally preserved. The public library is expected to offer different kinds of services to users, these includes reference, extension, audiovisual and training services. It is no exaggeration that most public library customers come from the general public of which the post secondary school students are part. Miller (1996) stated that "while the public library was created by the people for the people, the public will let it go when and if they don't have use or want it any more If the public library is to continue to exist, then the library will necessarily have to develop and serve its customers in the ways they desire."

Statement of the problem

It is a known fact that for people to advance in the process of education there must be access to relevant information in various formats. Public libraries are one way to provide people with reading materials; however, public libraries have shown little success in modern societies, particularly in the developing countries like Nigeria. Post secondary school students constitute a larger population of people that has potent of effecting correct changes in the society. They are part of the populace that will take on batons from the present elites. Therefore, it is necessary to find out what services are available in public libraries as information channel to meet the information needs of these vast categories of future leaders. It is on this background that this study is carried out to examine the role of public library service in meeting the information needs of post-secondary school student in selected public libraries in Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The main objectives of the study is to examine the role of public library service in meeting the information needs of post-secondary school students in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. Identify the information needs of post-secondary school students in the selected public libraries in Nigeria.
2. Examine the type of service available to the post-secondary school students in the selected public libraries in Nigeria.
3. Examine the influence of public library service on the information needs of post-secondary school students in Nigeria.
4. Investigate the purpose of use of library service to the post-secondary school students.
5. Investigate the major factors that hinder the public library services to the post secondary school students.

Research questions

The following are the research questions for the study:

1. What are the information needs of post-secondary school student in the selected public libraries in Nigeria?
2. What are the types of service available to the post-secondary school students in selected public libraries in Nigeria?
3. What influence does public library services have on the information needs of post-secondary school students in Nigeria?
4. What is the purpose for which the post-secondary school students use the public library service?
5. What are the major factors that hinder the public library service to the post secondary school students?

Significance of the study

This study is imperative to investigate the present status of the public library services. It is hoped that the findings of this study will provide some insights to the librarians and information professionals about information environment of post-secondary school students.

It is also hoped that this study will provide some insights to the policy makers in education ministry into the possibilities of establishing a more systematic, organized and comprehensive public and community library system for all category of students all over the state in particular and the country in general.

This study on the public library information service should help raise awareness of the post-secondary school students to the availability of public library service to meet their varying information needs.

In addition, the study will produce baseline data for information pertaining to information acquisition and utilization of post -secondary school students in Oyo, Ogun and kwara state, which will be very helpful for future studies in this area.

Scope of the study

The study covers three selected public libraries in three states of the federation. These are Oyo State Library Board, Ogun State Library Board, Kwara State Library Board and their users.

Literature Review

IFLA/UNESCO Public Library Manifesto (1994) stressed that the Public Library is the local center of information, making all kinds of knowledge and information readily available to its users. The services of the public library are provided on the basis of equality of access to all, regardless of age, race, sex, religion, nationality, language or social status. All age groups must find material relevant to their needs. Collections and services have to include all types of appropriate media and modern technologies as well as traditional materials.

The roles of public libraries are described in many documents, including manifestos. The first Public Library Manifesto was published in 1945 and later revised in 1972 and 1994. The IFLA/UNESCO Public Library Manifesto (1994) describes the role of public libraries as: "the local gateway to knowledge, provides a basic condition for lifelong learning, independent decision-making and cultural development for the individual and social groups" and "the public library as a living force for education, culture and information and as an essential agent for the fostering of peace and spiritual welfare through the minds of men and women." The public library is an important learning institution and serves a diverse clientele.

The public library system is in fact the seat of community lifelong learning – it offers opportunities for individuals and social groups to engage in learning – through leisure and information publications, multimedia formats including online sources, formalized programs and/or merely to learn by serendipity through browsing either the library shelves or surfing/ navigating the web (Kahlert, 2001). Libraries are, quite naturally, a source of

general information on virtually every topic imaginable. The importance of this function cannot be glossed over in the increasingly complex and confusing information-based society of today. Libraries are one of the few institutions in society that have a long history of specializing in organizing and in providing access to information. Libraries provide:

- a confidential and non-judgemental source of information on any topic, many of which can be very personal and highly sensitive in nature;
- assistance in the research process, especially to those who have never done research before;
- good tools for research via special collections, the reference collections, the reference collection, and the general collection; and
- answers to any questions that the public may have through reference service and
- referral to other agencies. (McClure and Bertot, 1998).

Ordinary, the public library has been considered as a purveyor of culture through the provision of literature and a provider of educational materials. In most developing countries, the education role has been extended not only to support the informal educational enrichment program needed by the lifelong learner, but also to serve as a resource for the development of reading habits of its public (Ahmad-Bakeri, 1998). Providing access to knowledge in a variety of formats to support formal and informal education has been the basis in the foundation and maintenance of most public libraries and remains the core purpose of the public library.

The main function of a public library is to acquire, select, organize and disseminate information needed by its users. It serves as a repository for the culture and recorded history of the people and as a place where people can go freely in search of information for self-education and pleasure. By performing these functions, a public library system will be in a position to enhance the educational, economics and social lives of the populace. It is expected that a public library will make its services available to all categories of users in the community regardless of race, colour, nationality, sex, religion, language and educational attainment (Salaam, 2001). He however noted that the original purpose of public library was to provide general reading materials and information services for adults. However, special services for different age groups and special users soon developed to meet the expanded demands on the libraries. The idea of the public library is not indigenous to Africa; it is an imported idea that came about as a result of western interaction with local people. Raseroka (1994) expressed the view that public libraries in Africa have to a great extent been established using the blue print provided by the public library tradition of developed countries. However, from the 1970s, local librarians trained abroad have taken over leadership of these libraries.

The UNESCO seminar on public library development in Africa, held at Ibadan in 1953, was the first international conference or seminar on libraries ever held in Africa. It gave further stimulus to Dr. Azikwe's quest for library services in Nigeria. It was only a catalyst – spurring on the champions of public or national libraries in African countries like Dr. Azikwe, and Dr. Nkrumah of the then Gold Coast (Ghana). It also helped to stimulate African governments to enact public library legislations and to set up public library boards. The seminar emphasized that “only legislation can empower the appropriate authorities to provide the services and ensure adequate financial support and efficient administration according to a national standard. Only legislation can define the functions of the providing authority, create the conditions in which it may fulfill those functions, and ensure development” (UNESCO cited by Aguolu and Aguolu, 1997).

Information needs of post Secondary School Students

Information needs and information-seeking are important factors aspects of life including work, school, health and recreation. Information needs come in different forms. There are dormant needs of which a person is unaware, unexpressed needs that are felt but not articulated and expressed needs that a person will try to resolve by sharing with a peer or a specialist (Devadson and Lingam, 1996; Nicholas, 2000).

There are two types of information needs that affect an individual: one dealing with the individual personally and one related to a group of which he is a member (for example, immigrants, students and police officers). Both kinds are affected by individuals and situational influence (Allen, 1996). Information-grounds are a social way of gathering information to satisfy both expressed and unexpressed needs of individuals and groups in a social environment. Many immigrants gather together and share knowledge without actually asking for information. These setting can include parks, language classes for immigrants, parties and other social contexts (Pettigrew 1999; Fisher et al. 2004). As mentioned earlier, studies have shown that social networking is one of the principle means by which information needs are satisfied.

Many scholars have examined the information needs of faculty members in Nigeria and elsewhere. For instance, the findings of Ajidahun (1990), Ehikhamenor (1990) and Jam (1992), establish that the information needs of faculty are job-related, specifically to teaching, research, and publication. This has been repeatedly emphasized in recent surveys. See for example, Njongmate and Ehikhamenor (1998); Odunsanya and Amusa (2003); Baker (2004); Bruce (2005); Macevieiute (2006) and Bigdeli (2007).

Jam (1992) finds that periodical and the predominant information materials used by academic staff in a survey of selected tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The extensive use of periodicals by faculty derives from the ability of those publications to provide current and up-to-date information; others who explored this include Olanlokun and Momoh (1994). This contrasts sharply with Baker (2004), who paints a general picture of increasing availability of information for professional and vocational undertakings. Baker elicits optimism that the information gap is being addressed; however, Whittaker (1997) and Popoola (2001) caution that availability of information resource and services do not automatically translate to information accessibility and use.

Awokoya (1988) and Adimorah (1993) describe the constraints on effective information delivery to academic staff in technological and tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Such constraints include inadequate information centres, inadequate library staff, lack of relevant information materials, inconvenient hours, and absence of information and communication technologies (ICTs). Isah (1995) and Edem and Bassey (1990), in separate studies, recommend increased library funding, departmentalization of library services, and provision of current information resources to ameliorate difficulties associated with information search and retrieval in Nigeria university libraries.

The library and information Commission (1998) has claimed that libraries and information services of all kinds are catalysts for learning. They are intimately related to learner's needs and already offer quality learning places in their many different environments. The library may achieve this through the provision of:

- gateways and access to information, advice, guidance and quality assurance;
- opportunity to learn by providing resources of an appropriate range and quality;
- personal support for learners;
- accessibility through resources and expertise at times and places convenient to learners;
- a supportive environment;
- staff skilled in supporting learners and the learning process; and
- resource in all formats.
- Links to other learning resources through partnership (Library Association 2001).

Many writers have in various ways described precisely the role of the public libraries. Muhammed (2006) stated that the public library is concerned with the refreshment of man's spirit by the provision of books for relaxation and pleasure. He further states that the public library, through various forms of activities such as indexing, abstracting and classification is able to group multiple and interdisciplinary nature of knowledge into logical arrangement so that communities use the materials without difficulties.

American Library Association cited in Muhammed (2006) maintained that the public library supplies materials and services to a community in order to support the community's educational, informational, cultural and recreational needs.

Ang (2001) gave six approaches to the role of public libraries in "postmodern" society:

1. The public library emerges as the community's market place where people meet and discuss things. It presents a space reserved for free debate and open thinking, a public floor for dialog, education and experiences. There are no limits to communication between visitors and to the acquiring of knowledge-worldwide and multi-media. The public library is a place of lifelong learning, an open university. It will satisfy the needs of tomorrow's society and offer everything to almost everybody.
2. The public library may act as the community's information switchboard. At the library, the customer can become acquainted with data on their community, communicate with leading administrators, create own information, and offer to help producing community information or with other assignments. This way, the library becomes an open agency for information and news. Thus, the public library will slowly take on the features of a multimedia workshop.
3. Information services free of charge and the inter-library network are almost unique as an infrastructure. These networks guarantee the libraries future and ought to be maintained and developed in view of the competitors. In the world of the future, it will turn out to be of particular importance to librarians to help one another in systematizing useful information from the information highway.
4. Services at a distance will be possible, i.e. the public library is delivering its services to our homes via digital technology. This include all of the internet, CD-ROMs, utility programs, the library catalog, etc. in this field, vast vistas open up to the public library.
5. The public library needs to open up to the world outside in order to find useful partners for its development and to co-operate with them in the market. In the first place, these will include trade and industry, especially the IT sector. It is important to contact the trade and industries units in public authorities as well as the think tanks of public institutions. In general, the library as such has to make itself better known. Thus, the greatest challenge is to find partners outside the traditional work domain of culture. This holds true for *marketing*, too, where the public library needs to make an extra effort. In the public sector it becomes ever more important to make allies with the universities. The public library will, amongst other things, be the natural offshoot of the university in its vicinity.

Distance education is on the increase, which means additional tasks for the public library. Anyway, the educational system at all levels is the most important institution to gain as a co-operation partner. *Lifelong learning* is established as a familiar concept. The public library will have to go beyond its traditions if it wants to keep up with change in our age.

6. In the future, the public library needs to have new ideas in order to survive – just like any other tax-based organization or commercial business. The library will have to procure funding from new sources, i.e. engage in fundraising. The modern public library needs its own computer and development as well as a special unit for marketing and fundraising.

Population of the Study

The target population for this study is the post secondary school students who make use of the public library resources and service to satisfy their daily and basic information needs. This category of users spread across three state public libraries in Nigeria. These libraries are the Oyo State Library Board, Ogun State Library Board and Kwara State Library Board.

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

The sampling method adopted for the purpose of this study is the simple random sampling technique. The sampled respondents for this study will be drawn from the post secondary students of the selected state public libraries. Meanwhile, about fifty respondents were randomly selected from each of the three selected public libraries, giving a total of 150 respondents selected for this study.

Research Instrument

Data was gathered by using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire in this study was divided into two sections. Sections A contain the demographic information of respondents' such as name, sex, age, level of study and course of study. Section B contains questions regarding experience in use of library resources and service as well as their information needs. The questionnaire was made up of Likert-type scale questions on available library resources and services, information needs of users, frequency of use of library by users, and the problems of using the public libraries. The Likert-type questions were measured using the following scales: SA = Strongly Agreed; A = Agreed; D = Disagreed; SD = Strongly Disagreed.

Methods of Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed using frequency counts and percentages. The result was presented in the table formats.

Data Analysis and Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study are presented in a descriptive form using frequencies and percentages.

Questionnaire response rate

Table 4.1: Response rate

S/No	Public Library	No Sampled	No Returned
1.	Oyo State Library Board	50	49(98%)
2.	Ogun State Library Board	50	48(96%)
3.	Kwara State Library Board	50	49(98%)
	Total	150	145(96.7%)

A total of one hundred and fifty (150) copies of the questionnaire were administered on the respondents in three selected state public libraries in Oyo, Ogun and Kwara States. Fifty (50) copies were administered to the post secondary school students in each of the public libraries. Overall, 145 copies were returned making a total of 96.7% response rate.

Demographic characteristics of the respondents**Table 4.2 : Age distribution of the respondents**

Age Range	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18-25	67	46.2
26-35	43	29.7
36-45	16	11.0
46-55	14	9.7
Over 56	5	3.4
Total	145	100.0

Table 4.2 above showed that out of the 145 respondents, majority 67(46.2%) were between 18 and 25 years old followed by 43(29.7%) respondents, who were within 26 and 35 years of age. About 16(11%) of the respondents were between 36 and 45 years old while 14(9.7%) of them were from 46 to 55 years of age, and 3.4% respondents were over 56 years old. The result shows that tertiary institution students make use of public library.

Table 4.3: Gender distribution of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	91	62.8
Female	51	35.2
No response	3	2.1
Total	145	100.0

Table 4.3 revealed that majority, 91(62.8%) of the respondents were male while 51(35.2%) of them were female. These respondents cut across the three State Library Boards, which were Oyo State Library Board, Ogun State Library Board and Kwara State Library Board. This result was consistent with the finding of Ogunmodede and Emeahara (2010) who posited that Male undergraduates use the library more than their female counterparts.

Table 4.4: Marital status of the respondents

Marital status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Single	88	60.7
Married	48	33.1
Widowed	6	4.1
No Response	3	2.1
Total	145	100.0

Table 4.4 revealed that the highest number of respondents, 88(60.7%) were single. This was closely followed by the married who were 48(33.1%) respondents. The number of respondents who were widowed was only 6(4.1%) while 3(2.1%) decline responses. It could be deduced from the above result that majority of the user of public libraries were single.

Table 4.5: Level of education of the respondents

Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
WASCE/SSCE or equivalent	51	35.2
OND	30	20.7
Diploma	12	8.3
HND	5	3.4
First Degree	18	12.4
Masters	20	13.8
Ph.D.	--	--
No response	9	6.2
Total	163	100.0

The above table revealed that the highest number of respondents, 51(35.2%) had WASCE/SSCE or its equivalent. This was closely followed by those with ND who were 30(20.7%) respondents. The respondents with

Masters degree were 20(13.8%) while those with First degree were 18(12.4%). The implication of this is that holders of PhD do not use Public library, this may be, because they have academic library as an alternative.

Research question 1

What are the information needs of post-secondary school students in the selected state public libraries in Nigeria?

Table 4.6: Information needs of post secondary school students

S/No	Information needs	Frequency	Percentage %
1.	Information on personal development	60	41.4
2.	Information on academic work	90	62.1
3.	Job-related information	51	35.2
4.	Health-related information	48	33.1
5.	Sports news and recreation	66	45.5
6.	Research information	48	33.1

Table 4.6 showed that majority, 90(62.1%) of the respondents in the selected states public libraries indicated information on academic work as part of their information needs. 60(41.4%) of the post secondary school students in the selected public libraries also indicated that they needed information on personal development, while 66(45.5%) respondents affirmed that their information need was on sports news and recreation. Less than average respondents indicated they needed information on health related matter and on research information. From the findings, the various information needs of the post-secondary school students were on academic work, personal development and sports news and recreation. Generally speaking, not all the users in a library possess the same information needs; the needs vary from individual to individual. This therefore borders on the minority respondents who indicated their information needs as health-related information, research information and job-related information. The finding corroborated the earlier finding of Adedibu and Adio (1997).

Research question 2

What are the types of services available to the post-secondary school students in the selected public libraries?

Table 4.7: Types of services provided in the public libraries

S/No	Services	Frequency	Percentage %
1.	Lending services	118	81.4
2.	Reference services	108	74.5
3.	Photocopy services	48	33.1
4.	Internet access	57	39.3
5.	Referral services	72	49.7
6.	Provision of reading materials	141	97.2
7.	CD-ROM database search	26	17.9
8.	Online Public Access Catalogue	19	13.1
9.	Alerting users on arrival of new books or journal articles	52	35.9
10.	Library use instruction	32	22.1

Most of the respondents 118(81.4%) affirmed that the college libraries provide lending services to the users. Likewise, about 108(74.5%) of the respondents agreed that reference services was available in the libraries, and 141(97.2%) respondents indicated that the libraries provided reading materials. However, the provision of other services like internet access, referral services, and CD-ROM database search, photocopy services, library use instruction and Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) were all rated very low by the respondents from the three public libraries.

From the above result, it could be observed that the available library services include lending services, reference services and provision of reading materials. In spite of the low rating of the internet access, library use instruction (orientation) and referral services by the respondents, it was observed from personal investigation that these services were actually available to users in the libraries. In addition to these services were library extension services. Meanwhile, other services like Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC), CD-ROM database search, photocopy services, as well as alerting users on new arrivals were not available to post-secondary school

students in the public libraries. The result agreed with the finding of Atwi and Bello (1990) who posited that provision of reading material top the services provided by public libraries investigated.

It was noted that the low rating of some services in the public libraries by the post-secondary school students was that most of them were not aware of these services and as a result, they could not access them. It thus becomes very imperative for the public libraries to ensure that adequate awareness programmes are carried out to expose the users to the available services for better patronage.

Research question 3

What influence does public library services have on the information needs of post secondary school students in the selected public libraries in Nigeria?

Table 4.8: Influence of public library services

S/No	Influence of library services	SA	A	D	SD
1.	Access to photocopy facilities	18(12.4%)	15(10.3%)	40(27.6%)	19(13.1%)
2.	Access to loan facilities (book borrowing)	30(20.7%)	41(28.3%)	14(9.7%)	10(6.9%)
3.	Access to journals and serials materials like newspapers and magazines	47(32.4%)	59(40.7%)	3(2.1%)	--
4.	Conducive reading environment	29(20%)	49(33.8%)	32(22.1%)	5(3.4%)
5.	Access to recent and up-to-date library materials	10(6.9%)	41(28.3%)	52(35.9%)	7(4.8%)
6.	Access to internet facilities	13(9.0%)	50(34.5%)	25(17.2%)	19(13.1%)
7.	Access to reference resources	30(20.7%)	53(36.6%)	20(13.8%)	7(4.8%)
8.	Access to free online/electronic resources	2(1.4%)	25(17.2%)	54(37.2%)	29(20%)
9.	Helps me to meet my information needs at all times	8(5.5%)	50(34.5%)	43(29.7%)	13(9%)

Table 4.8 revealed the positive influence of public library services on the information needs of post-secondary school students. Majority of the post-secondary school students 106(73.1%) agreed that the public library services had really influenced their information needs in terms of access to journals and serials materials like newspapers and magazines, access to reference resources 83(57.3%) and conducive reading environment 78(53.8%). Only few of the respondents 27(18.6%) agreed that the public libraries provided them with access to free online/electronic resources, while majority of them disagreed. The result corroborated the view of Oyegade, Nassarawa and Mokogwu (2003) on the services rendered to the public library while speaking on forty years of library service to Nigeria.

The results of the study revealed that public library services had in one way or the other influenced the information needs of post-secondary school students. These included but not limited to access to journals and serials materials like newspapers and magazines, access to reference resources and conducive reading environment. Other influences on the respondents' information needs were access to loan facilities (book borrowing), and access to internet facilities. It was noted that the post secondary school students could not access free online/electronic resources in the libraries simply because despite the fact that these services were available, they were strictly fee-based, that is, users must pay a token before they could access the services.

Research question 4

What is the purpose for which the post-secondary school students used the public libraries?

Table 4.9: Purpose of use of public libraries

S/No	Purpose	Frequency	Percentage %
1.	Personal development	48	33.1
2.	To support my academic activities	90	62.1
3.	Recreation and entertainment	51	35.2
4.	Current affairs	48	33.1
5.	For examination purpose	66	45.5
6.	Decision making processes	48	33.1

Table 4.9 revealed that majority 90(62.1%) of the respondents used the public library to support their academic activities. 66(45.5%) of the respondents also used the public libraries for examination purposes, while the least of the respondents 48(33.1%) affirmed that they used the public libraries for personal development and decision-making processes, and current affairs respectively.

As it was revealed in the above result, majority of the post secondary school students used the public libraries mainly to support academic activities. Quite a number of them also used the libraries for other purposes such as preparation for examination, recreation and entertainment, personal development, current affairs and decision-making processes.

Research question 5

What are the major factors that hinder the public library services to the post-secondary school students?

Table 4.10: Factors that hinder the public library services

S/No	Factors	Frequency	Percentage %
1.	Inadequate information resource	75	51.7
2.	Inadequate power supply to access the internet	69	47.6
3.	Inadequate seating space	31	21.4
4.	The library environment is not conducive for reading	40	27.6
5.	Lack of relevant materials to meet my needs	51	35.2
6.	Inability to get useful information from the library most times	63	43.4
7.	Non cooperation of other library staff	56	38.6
8.	Poor network/internet connectivity	48	33.1

As regards the factors that hinder the public library services to the post-secondary school students, only the inadequate information resources was indicated by more than half 75(51.7%) of the respondents. Less than half of the respondents 69(47.6%) indicated inadequate power supply to access the internet, while only few 31(21.4%) of the respondents indicated inadequate seating space.

It was observed from the result that inadequate information resources was the only prominent factor against the public library services that was peculiar to majority of the post-secondary school students. Although, other factors against the effectiveness of public library services were also indicated by the respondents such as inadequate power supply to access the internet, and inability to get useful information from the library most times, but they were not that serious because only few of these respondents experienced these problems. The above finding was in line the findings of Okpara (2008) and Muhammed (2006).

Table 4.11: Ways to improve public library services

S/No	Ways	Frequency	Percentage %
1.	Maintain high quality of print collections	75	51.7
2.	Provide training in use of Web/library resources	90	62.1
3.	Increase library hours	38	26.2
4.	Positive change of library staff attitude to users	71	49.0
5.	Improve the level of internet connectivity	88	60.7
6.	Library materials should be well organized for easy retrieval	82	56.6
7.	The OPAC system should be made more functional	68	46.9
8.	Organizing display and exhibition to market the resources and services to library users	66	45.5

As shown in Table 4.11 above, the public libraries need to take some urgent steps to be able to improve the library services and as well ensure high level of user satisfaction. Not fewer than 90(62.1%) respondents indicated that the public libraries should provide training in the use of Web/library resources. 88(60.7%) affirmed that the level of internet connectivity should be improved. The least of the respondents 38(26.2%) indicated that the libraries should increase their operation hours. Other ways by which the public library services can be improved is that libraries should maintain a high quality of print collections, and better organization of library materials for easy retrieval. Although, quite a number of the respondents also suggested that the library OPAC should be made more functional, organize display and exhibition to market the resources and services to library users, and ensure the positive change of library staff attitude to users.

CONCLUSION

The major reason for which the public libraries were set up was to cater for the information needs of the community which they serve. This objective has to a greater extent been achieved by the public libraries through the provision of various information resources and services to meet the needs of their diverse users (including post-secondary school students). The public libraries provide services like lending, reference, extension, internet, reading materials and library use instruction services to meet the needs of the post-secondary school students. The post-secondary school students and other numerous users rely on the public library services in order to support their academic activities, prepare for examinations, recreation and entertainment, personal development, current affairs and decision-making processes. However, in this process, they also face certain impediments like inadequate information resources, inadequate power supply to access the internet, and inability to get useful information from the library which the libraries must do all things possible to provide solutions to, in order to make the services provision very effective and also satisfy users' needs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study.

1. The public libraries should ensure that relevant, current and adequate information resources in the various formats like prints and electronic are made available in the libraries so that the post-secondary school students and other users can have access to them and help them meet their various information needs regularly.
2. The public libraries should endeavour to teach the students library use skills to enable them exploit the richness of the library resources and services so that they can be able to meet their information needs.
3. Adequate computer with internet facilities and other electronic resources should also be acquired and made more readily available for use in the public libraries. This is to complement the print resources which are already available in the library as well as enable the users to have access to online resources and databases.
4. The public libraries should endeavour to increase their bandwidth in order to solve the problem of poor internet/network connectivity as well as reduce the fluctuations in the network.
5. Provision should be made for alternative power supply in the public libraries. This will no doubt help a lot in solving the problem of inadequate power supply to access the internet.
6. The public libraries should device means of creating the users awareness to the library resources and services. This will help increase the level of awareness of the library users to the available resources and services in the libraries for better patronage.

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